

Parallel Subdomain Coupling for non-matching Meshes in Alya

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Abstract

Domain Composition Methods are techniques to couple local solutions of physical problems, solved on local meshes, to obtain a global solution on the union of these meshes. This work consisted in implementing such techniques at the algebraic level, making the coupling independent of the physics to be considered. This approach enables us to solve multi-domain and multi-physics problems, using both single and multi-code approaches. Both explicit and implicit coupling were implemented, for surface and volume couplings. The implementation was carried out for distributed memory supercomputers, using MPI. Several physical examples demonstrate the reliability of the proposed implementation.

Introduction

Domain Composition Methods (usually referred to as Domain Decomposition Methods in the literature) are techniques to couple local solutions to physical problems, solved on local meshes, to obtain a global solution on the union of these meshes. On the one hand, the local physics can be the same, for example to couple a fluid on a moving subdomain to the same fluid on a fixed subdomain; examples of methods to treat such problems are the Chimera, Shear-Slip Mesh Update and sliding mesh methods. On the other hand, the physics can be different and therefore the coupling is referred to as multi-physics. Let us mention for example, thermal flow to conjugate heat transfer, fluid-structure interaction (FSI), particle tracking, etc.

In the literature, many methodologies have been proposed to envisage DCM: they are mesh-based, formulation-based, or algebraic-based. In mesh-based formulations, the coupling is achieved at the mesh level, before the governing equations are assembled into an algebraic system (mesh conforming, Shear-Slip Mesh Update, HERMESH). The formulation-based counterpart recomposes the solution from the strong or weak formulation itself, and is implemented during the assembly of the algebraic system on the subdomain meshes. The different coupling techniques can be formulated at the strong and continuous level, at the weak and continuous/discrete level (iteration-by-subdomains, mortar element, mesh free interpolation). Although the different methods usually lead to the same solutions at the continuous level, which usually coincide with the solution of the problem on the original domain, they have very different behaviors at the discrete level and accept very different implementations. Eventually, algebraic-based formulations treat the composition of the solutions directly on the matrix and right-hand side of the individual subdomain algebraic systems.

The objective of the work was to implement coupling strategies in the context of DCM, in Alya multi-physics code, with the following requirements:

- Multi-physics coupling
- Multi-code coupling
- Algebraic-based formulation
- Non-matching meshes
- Explicit and Implicit coupling
- Distributed memory

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Methodology

The coupling methodologies are extensively described in [1]. The idea is the following. Let us assume we have two disjoint subdomains, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Two-domain composition: nomenclature.

We want to couple the solution of subdomain 1 to that of subdomain 2. At the algebraic level, individual systems read:

$$\mathbf{A}_1 \mathbf{u}_1 = \mathbf{b}_1, \quad \mathbf{A}_2 \mathbf{u}_2 = \mathbf{b}_2$$

Now, by imposing a Dirichlet/Neumann coupling at the algebraic level, and introducing transmission matrices \mathbf{T}^D and \mathbf{T}^N for the Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions, respectively, we obtain the following coupled system:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{11} & \mathbf{A}_{1\Gamma_1} \\ 0 & \mathbf{I} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u}_1 \\ \mathbf{u}_{\Gamma_1} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{b}_1 \\ \mathbf{T}^D \mathbf{u}_{\Gamma_2} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{22} & \mathbf{A}_{2\Gamma_2} \\ \mathbf{A}_{\Gamma_2 2} & \mathbf{A}_{\Gamma_2 \Gamma_2} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u}_2 \\ \mathbf{u}_{\Gamma_2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{b}_2 \\ \mathbf{b}_{\Gamma_2} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{T}^N (\mathbf{b}_{\Gamma_1} - \mathbf{A}_{\Gamma_1 1} \mathbf{u}_1 - \mathbf{A}_{\Gamma_1 \Gamma_1} \mathbf{u}_{\Gamma_1}) \end{pmatrix}$$

For matching meshes on the interfaces ($\mathbf{T}^D = \mathbf{I}$ and $\mathbf{T}^N = \mathbf{I}$), should this system converge, it converges to the one-domain monolithic solution. As shown in [1], this coupled system can be solved in two ways. On the one hand, explicit coupling is achieved by solving the systems in subdomain 1 and 2, independently, using the solution of the other system from a previous iteration, to interpolate the Dirichlet and Neumann conditions. On the other hand, the coupling can be implicit by exchanging the transmission conditions each time a matrix-vector product is carried out in the iterative solver, exactly as parallelization techniques are implemented. Both strategies have been implemented. The implementation is almost identical for explicit and implicit couplings, and can be divided into two steps:

- A *preprocessing step*, to set up the data structure for parallel exchange
- An *assembly step*, which consists in exchanging the transmission conditions in a distributed memory context, and assembling them.

Implementation

General aspects

This section is devoted to implementation issues, with special emphasis on the parallelization aspects, in a distributed memory context. The DCM presented in the previous section was implemented in Alya, a high performance computational mechanics code developed at BSC-CNS, extensively described in [2]. One important point of interest here is the parallelization strategy of Alya. The mesh is partitioned using METIS [3], and the coupling of the partitions is mainly present in the iterative solvers and involves:

- Global communications to compute scalar products
- Point-to-point communications to assemble the results of each matrix-vector product.

Additional communications may be required to assemble complex preconditioners, but are not of interest in the following. As mentioned before, the implicit coupling is achieved through point-to-point inter-subdomain communications, after the intra-subdomain exchange has been carried out. The procedure is illustrated in Figure 2.

Matrix-vector product using n_p partitions:

Figure 2: Implicit coupling achieved at matrix-vector product level.

Let us first introduce some notations, illustrated in Figure 3. The target surface is the surface where a transmission condition, either Dirichlet or Neumann, is imposed. The source surface is the surface where this transmission condition is computed from. On the target surface we identify three more entities: the target boundary element, the target nodes and the target points. The target points can be nodes or Gauss points, whether the transmission condition is carried out through interpolation or through projection. The target nodes are the nodes belonging to target boundaries, where the transmission condition is assembled after each matrix-vector product, as both Dirichlet and Neumann algebraic transmission conditions are imposed node-wise.

Figure 3: Coupling terminology.

MPI environment

Implicit coupling is achieved within the same Alya instance, while explicit coupling is achieved in a multi-code environment via different levels of MPI communicator splitting, illustrated in Figure 4. This technique enables to setup in an easy way intra and inter subdomain communications.

Figure 4: MPI communicator splitting to enable intra- and inter-subdomain communications

Preprocessing step

In a distributed memory context, the mesh is divided into np partitions. Figure 5 shows an example of a DCM to couple two subdomains, partitioned into seven partitions in total.

Figure 5: Two-domain coupling with 7 partitions.

In this example, we depicted a particular target point of subdomain 1. This target point is a node of subdomain 1 if an interpolation scheme is considered, or an integration point if a projection scheme is selected instead. The first question to ask is: which partition can interpolate the values of a particular target point? As we are working in a distributed memory environment, the partitions have a-priori no direct access to the meshes of other partitions. Therefore, all queries must be carried out through MPI. To limit the information traffic through the network, one possibility consists in using the bounding boxes of the partitions to reduce the number of queries. We can imagine faster algorithms as well as binary trees or oct-trees to reduce the number of queries further more. For the moment, let us stick to the simplest option consisting in using only the bounding boxes. For each target point \mathbf{x}_t of each parallel partition of the mesh, we apply the procedure described in Algorithm 1.

After carrying out this algorithm, each partition with target points knows the list of target points hosted by each partition p . And these partitions know they host these target points. They are therefore able to construct a scheduling to exchange data on these target points, and the assembly can be carried out.

Algorithm 1 Find the host partition p_{host} of a target point \mathbf{x}_t

Input: target point coordinate \mathbf{x}_t .

Output: host partition p_{host} of \mathbf{x}_t .

1. `MPI_SEND`(\mathbf{x}_t) to partitions p 's whenever \mathbf{x}_t is in their bounding box.
 2. Partition p computes projection of \mathbf{x}_t onto their source boundary. d_p is the distance between \mathbf{x}_t and the projection point.
 3. `MPI_RECV`(d_p) from the p 's.
 4. Identify the partition p_{host} with the minimum distance.
 5. `MPI_SEND`(p_{host}) to the p 's partitions to inform them of the result of the minimization. Partition $p = p_{\text{host}}$ will be in charge of target point \mathbf{x}_t .
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Assembly step

The assembly step consists in exchanging the transmission conditions using the inter-subdomain communicator and to assemble them as a Dirichlet or a Neumann contribution. For explicit coupling, the cost of such an

operation is negligible compared to the costs of the assembly process of local matrices and that of the iterative solvers. For implicit coupling, this is not the case as the exchange is carried out after each matrix-vector product. Figure 6 shows an example of intra- and inter-communication in a matrix-vector product of an iterative solver. On the left part of the figure we represent 10 iterations (involving 20 matrix-vector products) of the BiCGSTAB solver applied to an advection-diffusion equation. On the right part of the figure, we can observe the trace of one single product. Here we have two subdomains, partitioned independently by METIS. We first note a very high load imbalance to compute the matrix vector product in each subdomain (blue lines). This is due to the fact that subdomain 1 is meshed with tetrahedra and subdomain 2 with hexahedra and because METIS load balances the elements. Therefore subdomain 1 has more or less six times less nodes than subdomain 2, which implies a six times less cost for matrix-vector product. We can also observe the intra-subdomain communications, carried out just before the inter-subdomain one. In this case, both have more or less the same duration. We conclude that the inter-subdomain communication should be further optimized, for example through a communication scheduling. Let us note, however, that in this example, the wet surface between the subdomains is quite large compared to the sizes of the subdomains.

Figure 6: Example of trace of a matrix-vector product involving coupling. Blue: CPU working. Red: idle CPU. Orange: global communication. Yellow arrows: point-to-point communication. (Left) Ten iterations. (Right) One single matrix-vector product.

Test cases

Test cases for implicit coupling: Navier-Stokes

The Navier-Stokes equations were solved in a square cavity test problem, the details of the configuration of the problem are presented in [1]. The domain is split into two subdomains as shown in Figure 7 (Right). A comparison between the results of the one-domain problem in two different resolution meshes and two different resolution meshes for the subdomain approach is presented in Figure 7 (Left). The subdomain approach reproduces accurately the solution of the one domain approach.

Figure 7: Implicit coupling applied to the Navier-Stokes equations [1]. (Left) Meshes (Right) Velocity and pressure.

Test case for explicit coupling: FSI

The described techniques were applied to multi-physics problems in the multi-code approach. In this case, we can consider the subdomains as the different codes. First, fluid structure interaction (FSI) problems were solved, this kind of problems are of great interest in bio-mechanical investigation as well as in engineering applications, and given that extremely scalable codes exists for both, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and for computational solid dynamics (CSD), the multi-code approach is particularly appealing in the parallel context [4].

In addition to the parallel strategies to define the needed interpolations discussed in the previous section, the multi-code coupling for FSI needs also a special treatment, in the present case the coupling cycle is as follows:

- Solve the fluid mechanics problem with the position of the deformable body coming from the solid solver, which in this case is Alya-solidz
- With the calculated solution, calculate the forces on the contact surface and send it to the solid solver (residual of momentum equation)
- Solve the solid mechanics problem subjected to the stresses coming from the fluid solver, in this case Alya-nastin
- Send the new configuration to the fluid solver (Dirichlet boundary condition)

Iterations over the described cycle are usually needed in order to obtain an accurate solution of the problem. The full description of the test case and the results obtained is given in [4]. A typical result for the velocity field and the deformed body is given in Figure 8.

Figure 8: FSI benchmark. (Left) Geometry. (Right) Results.

Test cases for explicit coupling: Navier-Stokes and particle transport

Another interesting application is the Lagrangian transport of particles, which is relevant in the study of particle deposition in the respiratory system for example. In this case, a CFD problem is solved using Alya-nastin, the resulting velocity field is interpolated in the points defined in the pre-process step and is sent to the particles transport code, in this case Alya-partis. For this application, there is no feedback to the fluid domain coming from the particles, thus no special treatment of the multi-code coupling is needed. A detailed description of the

results for such cases is presented in [5]. Typical results for this case are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Coupling for particle transport in a fluid. (Left) Strategy. (Right) Results.

Conclusions

We have implemented a strategy to couple subdomains with non-matching meshes for distributed memory supercomputers. The method can be explicit (multi code) or implicit (single code). The latter one was implemented using a MPI communicator splitting in order to set inter- and intra-subdomain communicator. This enabled us not to affect the original parallelization of the code. In addition, the methodology is currently being tested for multi-physics simulations, like: fluid-structure interactions; fluid-particle coupling; contact problems; thermal flows coupled with conjugate heat transfer.

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